

COMPARING WELFARE LEVELS ACROSS INDONESIA'S ARCHIPELAGIC DISTRICTS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: EVIDENCE FROM TALAUD, SANGIHE, AND MOROTAI

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Abstract

National development should aim to improve the citizens' quality of life through economic growth, social progress, and environmental sustainability. This involves creating conditions that support the growth of businesses, industries, and infrastructure while protecting the environment and preserving natural resources for future generations. Indonesia is the world's largest archipelagic nation, endowed with rich and diverse natural resources, where marine fisheries play an important role in developing the regions. The utilization of these resources, however, appears to be rather limited in various areas. This study compares economic welfare levels in the archipelagic districts of Talaud, Sangihe, and Morotai, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. The results indicate that the Sangihe Islands have a higher average income and lower poverty levels compared to Talaud and Morotai Islands. These findings call for the need for targeted forms of social protection, inclusive economic policies, and improved access to public services. The evidence may further inform the policymakers and stakeholders as they design programs to address regional disparities and mitigate the socioeconomic impacts of the pandemic in remote island communities.

Keywords: Economic Development; Welfare; Income; Poverty; Fisheries Resources.

1. BACKGROUND

The success of a country's development is often reflected in the well-being of its human capital alongside the sustainable management of its natural resources (Isham et al., 2002). Indonesia's natural resources are both diverse and unique, playing a crucial role in the livelihoods of its people (Henley, 2008; Dutu, 2015). As the world's largest archipelagic nation spanning approximately six million square miles (i.e., two-thirds of which consist of ocean), Indonesia relies heavily on fisheries, particularly marine fisheries, as a vital resource for supporting regional development (Halim et al., 2019). Despite the country's enormous fishery potential, the communities that depend on these resources have yet to fully benefit from or effectively utilize them. Thus, the government should implement various programs to effectively manage and harness the country's diverse potentials (e.g., March and Failler, 2022). By maximizing these resources, the overall welfare of the population can be significantly enhanced. In general, a significant portion of the Indonesian population continues to face challenges in achieving a prosperous standard of living (Hill, 2021). A society is considered prosperous when its members are able to meet their basic needs effectively. Welfare can be measured with several indicators, such as the economy and education. From an economic perspective, the community is prosperous when it meets its basic needs (e.g., clothing, food, and shelter). Meanwhile, from

an educational perspective, the community is said to be prosperous when people can obtain a quality education, which should be easily accessible. The ultimate goal of development is to create a just and prosperous society. To achieve this, available resources must be managed and utilized effectively and efficiently. Human development is a key objective of government programs, aimed at improving the overall quality of life for the population. This increased quality of life may bring people to a better living standard. Quality human resources are embodied in education, health, and the economy that improves over time. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the well-being and welfare of people worldwide. In Indonesia, the Archipelagic District is one of the areas that have been severely affected by the pandemic. With the implementation of various measures such as lockdowns, social distancing, and travel restrictions, the welfare level of people in the Archipelagic District has significantly been affected.

Even before the pandemic, the Archipelagic District faced persistent challenges, including poverty, unemployment, and limited access to adequate healthcare facilities. With the emergence of the pandemic, these challenges have been exacerbated, leading to a further decline in the welfare level of the people. Many individuals have lost their jobs due to business closures and reductions in economic activities, making it challenging for them to access necessities such as food, housing, and healthcare. The pandemic has also significantly impacted the mental health of individuals in the Archipelagic District. With the implementation of social distancing and travel restrictions, many people have been forced to isolate themselves from their families and communities. This isolation has led to increased anxiety, depression, and loneliness, which have further affected the welfare of the people.

Several studies have been conducted on the impact of COVID-19 on the welfare level of people in Indonesia (Suryahadi et al., 2021). However, limited research has focused specifically on the Archipelagic Districts. Therefore, this research fills this gap by examining the comparison of social welfare level in the Archipelagic District during the COVID-19 Pandemic, namely in the Talaud, Sangihe, and Morotai Islands. The findings of this research are expected to provide valuable insights into the challenges faced by the people in the Archipelagic District during the pandemic. The results of the study may also inform policymakers and other stakeholders about the measures that can be implemented to mitigate the impact of the pandemic on the welfare level of the people. Ultimately, the study aims to contribute to developing effective policies and programs that can improve the welfare level of people in the Archipelagic District during and beyond the COVID-19 pandemic.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section provides an understanding of the current state of knowledge on the research topic and helps to situate the research within the context of the broader research field. In particular, it provides a comprehensive analysis of the research that has already been conducted in the field, which helps to identify gaps in knowledge, identify relevant theories, and provide a framework for the research.

2.1. Community welfare

In general, the term community welfare is often interpreted as a prosperous condition (first conception), which is a state of fulfillment of all forms of life's needs, especially those that are basic in nature such as food, clothing, housing, education and health care. The definition of social welfare also refers to all activities of organizing and distributing social services for community groups, particularly disadvantaged groups. The implementation of various formal and informal social protection schemes is an example of social welfare activities (Sumadi, 2023).

Welfare theory in general can be classified into three types, namely classical utilitarian, neoclassical welfare theory and new contractarian approach (Sugiarto et al., 2002). First, the classical utilitarian approach, which emphasizes that one's pleasure or satisfaction can be measured and increased. The principle for the individual is to increase as much as possible the level of his welfare, while for society the increase in the welfare of his group is a principle that is held in his life. Second, the neoclassical welfare theory approach, which explains that the welfare function is a function of all individual satisfactions. Lastly, the new contractarian approach promotes maximum freedom in an individual's or someone's life. The most emphasized aspect in this new contractarian approach stresses that individuals will maximize their freedom to pursue their concept of goods and services without interference.

The welfare of the middle and lower classes can be represented from the level of people's lives. The living standard of the people is marked by the eradication of poverty, better levels of health, acquisition of higher levels of education, and levels of community productivity. Not only to improve the people's welfare, development also seeks to foster people's aspirations and demands for a better life. Development cannot only be viewed from the aspect of growth. One of the results of development that only applies the growth paradigm is the emergence of a gap between the rich and the poor, and rampant unemployment. Ultimately, growth is always associated with an increase in national income (gross national products).

2.2. Poverty

Poverty is a social problem that continues to exist in people's lives. The classic problem of poverty has existed for a very long time, and the main element of the problem is related to various forms or characters of human life. In other words, poverty is a universal problem and has become a world concern. This issue exists in all countries, even though the impact of poverty is very different. Poverty is always related to inequality and vulnerability (Cerra et al., 2021). Vulnerability is a key dimension of well-being because it influences individual behavior in terms of investment, production patterns and appropriate strategies and perceptions of one's own situation. Poverty may be caused by two things. The first is that poverty arises from the behavior of society or a person, namely: a) limitations of capital resources, which can be interpreted as the quality of human resources, for example skills, education, and knowledge, and b) place or geographic location of an area that is remote and difficult to reach, which makes it difficult to interact with advanced residents. Secondly, poverty may be caused by development policies or government policies, which can be seen from various aspects, namely:

a) development that pays little attention to areas or areas that are remote and difficult to reach, b) an imbalance between development in rural and urban areas, and c) lack of attention to small-scale community businesses and products or micro-economic businesses.

Poverty may be seen as a form of multidimensional problems (He et al., 2023). Specifically, poverty has four forms. The four forms of poverty are as follows. The first form is absolute poverty, which is a condition where the income of a person or group of people is below the poverty line so that it is insufficient to meet the standard needs for food, clothing, health, housing and education needed to improve the quality of life. The poverty line is defined as the average expenditure or average consumption for basic needs related to meeting welfare standards. This form of absolute poverty is most widely used as a concept to determine or define the criteria for a person or group of people to be called poor. The second form is relative poverty, which is defined as a form of poverty that occurs due to the influence of development policies that have not reached all levels of society, causing income inequality or inequality in welfare standards. Areas that have not been reached by development programs like this are generally known as underdeveloped areas.

The third form is cultural poverty, which is a form of poverty that occurs as a result of the attitudes and habits of a person or society that generally come from a culture or custom that is relatively unwilling to improve living standards with modern procedures. Habits like this can be in the form of being lazy, wasteful or never thrifty, less creative, and also relatively dependent on other parties. Lastly, the fourth form is structural poverty, which is a form of poverty caused by low access to resources which generally occurs in a socio-cultural or socio-political order that does not support poverty liberation. This form of poverty also sometimes has a discriminatory element. Structural forms of poverty are the forms of poverty that have received the most attention in the field of social science, especially among aid/lending countries such as the World Bank, IMF, and the Asian Development Bank. Structural forms of poverty are also considered the most likely to cause the three forms of poverty previously mentioned.

Based on its nature, poverty may be classified into two types. The types of poverty based on their nature are natural poverty and artificial poverty. Natural poverty is formed as a result of scarcity of natural resources and minimal or no public infrastructure (roads, electricity and clean water), and infertile soil conditions. Regions with these characteristics are generally areas that have not been covered by development policies so that they become underdeveloped areas. Furthermore, artificial poverty is caused by a modernization or development system that causes people to not have many opportunities to control resources, facilities and economic facilities evenly. Poverty like this is the negative impact of implementing the concept of development, which is generally carried out in developing countries. The goal of pursuing high economic growth targets results in an unequal distribution of development results where the industrial sector, for example, enjoys a higher level of benefits than those working in the agricultural sector.

The two types of poverty above are often associated with the concept of development, which has been implemented for a long time in developing countries in the 1970s and 1980s. The issue of poverty and discussion of the causes of poverty are still being debated (Lister, 2021),

both in the academic environment and at the level of development policy makers. One of the debates is to determine the definition of a person or group of people who are called poor. In general, poverty identification is only carried out on relatively measurable indicators such as per capita income and average consumption expenditure. The characteristics of poverty that are still used to determine the condition of being poor are: a) not having their own factors of production such as land, capital, work equipment, and adequate skills, b) having a relatively low level of education, c) working in a small scope and small capital or also called working in the informal sector environment so that they are sometimes also called underemployed, d) Located in rural areas or in areas far from regional growth centers or in certain urban areas (slum areas), and finally e) having a relatively low opportunity to obtain sufficient basic needs, including in obtaining health and education services in accordance with welfare standards in general. While the concept of poverty remains a subject of ongoing debate, the characteristics outlined above are among the most commonly recognized and discussed in relation to a country's economic development.

2.3. Related studies

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the welfare level of people in many regions around the world (Kozlovskiy et al., 2021; Cantó et al., 2022; Heryadi et al., 2023), including the Archipelagic District in Indonesia (Harapan et al., 2023). The pandemic's impact has been especially profound on food systems, livelihoods, public health, and family welfare, prompting various researchers to explore these effects in different contexts. This literature review aims to provide an overview of the current research on the welfare level of people in the Archipelagic District during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Harapan et al. (2023) provided a comprehensive overview of Indonesia's pandemic response, highlighting the unique challenges posed by the country's vast archipelagic geography. Their study outlines how socio-economic conditions shaped the public health system's ability to respond to the crisis, detailing Indonesia's efforts in testing, vaccination, and containment, while also pointing to the limitations and complexities in implementing these measures uniformly across regions.

At the community level, the agricultural sector faced both behavioral and welfare disruptions. Heryadi et al. (2023) investigated the effects of the pandemic on organic rice farmers in East Priangan, finding substantial behavioral changes across all agribusiness subsystems, from input procurement to marketing and support services. These behavioral shifts were statistically significant and correlated with a decline in farmers' welfare. The study emphasized the need to reconfigure agribusiness development models that are responsive to the new realities imposed by the pandemic, including shocks to both supply chains and market access.

Food insecurity emerged as another pressing concern during the pandemic. Anwar and Nasrudin (2021) conducted a geospatial analysis using Susenas data to assess the severity of food insecurity across Indonesia's archipelago. Their findings revealed stark regional disparities, with eastern regions like Papua and Maluku experiencing higher levels of severe food insecurity. The study identified both demand and supply-side disruptions (ranging from

limited physical access to food due to mobility restrictions to reduced economic access resulting from income losses) as key drivers of food vulnerability during the pandemic. This research underscores the pandemic's potential to exacerbate existing inequalities and push previously secure households into food-insecure conditions.

Beyond economic and agricultural sectors, family welfare and resilience were also deeply affected. Sunarti et al. (2022) captured the lived experiences of Indonesian families during the first year of the pandemic through a large-scale online survey. Their study highlighted that economic pressures, heightened stress, and disrupted food security negatively affected both psychological and social welfare. However, families also demonstrated resilience by optimizing internal coping strategies such as resource management, increased interaction, and religious devotion. Interestingly, economic pressure was also linked to improved communication and time management within families, suggesting adaptive responses amidst crisis. The study concluded that child welfare significantly influences overall family resilience, which is further strengthened by food coping strategies and social support.

The tourism sector, another critical component of Indonesia's economy, also faced unprecedented challenges. King et al. (2021) examined the vulnerability of marine tourism operations in eastern Indonesia using a livelihood resilience framework. Their findings indicated that the prevailing development paradigm, favoring high-end tourism, often neglected local communities' livelihood capital, thereby reducing socio-ecological resilience. The pandemic served as a moment for critical reflection, calling for a reimagining of tourism as a means to empower communities and promote sustainable, inclusive development models that are better equipped to withstand future disruptions.

Taken together, these studies demonstrate that the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia has not only disrupted economic and social structures but has also exposed pre-existing vulnerabilities across various sectors. They collectively advocate for more inclusive, resilient, and context-specific responses that take into account the diversity of Indonesia's geography, livelihoods, and social fabric. From agribusiness and tourism to food security and family dynamics, resilience-building and adaptive capacity have emerged as central themes in navigating and recovering from the pandemic's wide-ranging impacts.

3. DATA, SAMPLE AND METHOD

The type of data used in this research is secondary data taken from the Central Bureau of Statistics. The location of the study is North Sulawesi and Ternate, while the sample period is in the year of 2022. This research employed a quantitative analysis approach using a difference test method. Specifically, the independent samples t-test was used to determine whether there is a significant difference between the mean values of two unrelated groups. This test compares the difference between the two sample means relative to the standard error of that difference. The independent samples t-test is appropriate when comparing two distinct groups that have been subjected to the same treatment. It assumes that the mean differences are normally distributed. Overall, the t-test is used to assess whether the average values of two or more independent groups differ significantly from one another.

4. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

To compare two different objects, a difference test analysis was conducted using SPSS 26. As shown in Table 1, the results indicate that the average values of income (i.e., *Pendapatan*) and poverty (i.e., *Kemiskinan*) are higher in the Sangihe compared to the Morotai Islands.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for Morotai and Sangihe Islands

Group Statistics					
	Daerah	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pendapatan	Morotai	12	13.5958	1.23108	.35538
	Sangihe	12	24.4114	6.91352	1.99576
Kemiskinan	Morotai	12	499.7500	57.25878	16.52919
	Sangihe	12	1522.2500	81.67466	23.57744

Source: SPSS Data Processing 26

Table 2 presents the combined test results, which indicate significant differences in income and poverty between the Morotai Islands and the Sangihe Islands. This is supported by a significance level of 0.000.

Table 2: T-test results for income and poverty: Morotai and Sangihe Islands

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t-test for Equality of Means					
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Pendapatan	Equal variances assumed	30.695	.000	-5.335	22	.000	-10.81558	2.02716	-15.01965	-6.61152
	Equal variances not assumed			-5.335	11.697	.000	-10.81558	2.02716	-15.24511	-6.38606
Kemiskinan	Equal variances assumed	1.214	.282	-35.511	22	.000	-1022.50000	28.79427	-1082.21566	-962.78434
	Equal variances not assumed			-35.511	19.709	.000	-1022.50000	28.79427	-1082.62070	-962.37930

Source: SPSS Data Processing 26

Table 3 shows that the average values of income and poverty are higher in the Talaud Islands compared to the Morotai Islands.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics for Morotai and Talaud Islands

Group Statistics					
	Daerah	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pendapatan	Morotai	12	13.5958	1.23108	.35538
	Talaud	12	18.8075	4.64918	1.34210
Kemiskinan	Morotai	12	499.7500	57.25878	16.52919
	Talaud	12	879.2500	43.75786	12.63181

Source: SPSS Data Processing 26

Table 4 presents the combined test results, indicating significant differences in income and poverty between the Morotai Islands and the Talaud Islands, as evidenced by a significance level of 0.000.

Table 4: T-test results for income and poverty: Morotai and Talaud Islands

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t-test for Equality of Means					
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Pendapatan	Equal variances assumed	23.316	.000	-3.754	22	.001	-5.21167	1.38836	-8.09094	-2.33239
	Equal variances not assumed			-3.754	12.535	.003	-5.21167	1.38836	-8.22238	-2.20095
Kemiskinan	Equal variances assumed	1.168	.291	-18.242	22	.000	-379.50000	20.80328	-422.64336	-336.35664
	Equal variances not assumed			-18.242	20.581	.000	-379.50000	20.80328	-422.81653	-336.18347

Source: SPSS Data Processing 26

Table 5 shows that the average values of income and poverty are higher in the Sangihe Islands compared to the Talaud Islands.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics for Sangihe and Talaud Islands

Group Statistics					
	Daerah	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pendapatan	Sangihe	12	24.4114	6.91352	1.99576
	Talaud	12	18.8075	4.64918	1.34210
Kemiskinan	Sangihe	12	1522.2500	81.67466	23.57744
	Talaud	12	879.2500	43.75786	12.63181

Source: SPSS Data Processing 26

The combined test results indicate significant differences in income and poverty between the Sangihe Islands and the Talaud Islands, as evidenced by significance levels of 0.031 and 0.000, respectively.

Table 6: T-test results for income and poverty: Sangihe and Talaud Islands

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-Test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Pendapatan	Equal variances assumed	3.447	.077	2.330	22	.029	5.60392	2.40506	.61613	10.59170
	Equal variances not assumed			2.330	19.260	.031	5.60392	2.40506	.57466	10.63317
Kemiskinan	Equal variances assumed	3.952	.059	24.039	22	.000	643.00000	26.74805	587.52793	698.47207
	Equal variances not assumed			24.039	16.834	.000	643.00000	26.74805	586.52415	699.47585

Source: SPSS Data Processing 26

5. CONCLUSION

Studying the welfare level of people in the Archipelagic District during the COVID-19 pandemic is crucial, as it sheds light on the pandemic's impact on the socio-economic conditions of the population. The pandemic has disrupted various aspects of people's lives, including access to healthcare, education, and employment, as well as social and mental well-being. Understanding the extent of these disruptions is crucial in identifying the population's needs and formulating effective policies and interventions to address them. This study may also help policymakers and stakeholders to develop strategies that promote economic recovery, poverty reduction, and social progress while ensuring that the most vulnerable members of the population are not left behind. Overall, examining welfare levels in the Archipelagic District during the pandemic is important for ensuring the well-being of the population and promoting sustainable development.

We documented several important findings based on the results of independent samples t-tests. First, the average income and poverty levels are higher in the Sangihe Islands compared to the Morotai Islands. Second, the t-test results indicate significant differences in income and poverty levels between the Morotai and Sangihe Islands. Third, the Talaud Islands also show higher average income and poverty levels compared to the Morotai Islands. Fourth, the differences in income and poverty between the Morotai and Talaud Islands are statistically significant. Fifth, the Sangihe Islands have higher income and poverty levels than the Talaud Islands. Finally, t-test results confirm significant differences in income and poverty between the Sangihe and Talaud Islands. Based on these findings, local governments are encouraged to manage existing resources more effectively (particularly fisheries resources) as Indonesia's rich marine potential can play a key role in boosting community income and alleviating poverty.

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